

Impact of Social Media on Contemporary Indonesian Language Usage

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ABSTRACT

Language is a very crucial sense of communication in culture and society. Indonesian as the official state language has a special role in maintaining Indonesian national and cultural identity. This research is qualitative research using descriptive analysis techniques with library research where this research attempts to describe existing phenomena, which are taking place currently or in the past. This research shows that social media has a significant impact on contemporary Indonesian language use. As a result, efforts need to be made to increase ethical awareness and the quality of the Indonesian language on these platforms. One step that can be taken is to provide education regarding the ethics and quality of using Indonesian on social media. Apart from that, there needs to be strict sanctions from law enforcement officials against social media users who violate the ethics and quality of the Indonesian language.

INTRODUCTION

In the emerging digital age, public media is an integral part of our everyday lives. This change has affected many aspects of life, including language usage. The Indonesian language, the official language of Indonesia, has undergone a crucial development in the context of the public media. Platforms like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and others have changed the way people communicate and interact in the use of language. Language is a sensory communication that is crucial to culture and citizens. Indonesian as the official language of the country has a special role in preserving the national identity and culture of Indonesia. However, the impact of social media on the use of contemporary Indonesian language is a phenomenon that deserves further exposure in the context of social, cultural, and technological change.

First of all, social media has spread the container of individual communication. With growing popularity, social platforms allow people to communicate and interact with a larger number of people around the world. This affects the use of the Indonesian language, where people can express themselves more freely, regardless of geographical constraints or physical environment. Therefore, contemporary Indonesian language on social media often reflects the broader cultural diversity and styles of communication.

In addition, social media has introduced many new features in communication, such as emoji, abbreviations, and slang. The use of emoticons, for example, allows for richer emotional expression and expression in social media conversations. These emoji can be an integral part of contemporary Indonesian language on these platforms. In addition, social media often facilitates the use of abbreviations and slang that create a more casual and informal language, unlike the formal language commonly used in traditional media.

The influence of social media on the use of the Indonesian language also covers the aspects of globalization. Social media facilitates connections with individuals from different countries and cultures, which also influences the way that Indonesia is spoken. There are many terms and phrases in English that have been translated or adopted into Indonesian language through social media. It describes how today's global culture influences the development of contemporary Indonesia. However, not only are positive changes in the use of the Indonesian language on social media, there are also potential negative impacts. For example, the use of rude language, insult, and inappropriate content is often found on social media. This could jeopardize the authenticity and quality of the Indonesian language as the official language of the country. In addition, problems related to proper understanding of the Indonesian language also arise, where social media users may misunderstand or ignore correct grammar norms.

With these various dynamics, it is important to understand how social media has affected the use of contemporary Indonesian language. This is important in the context of the preservation and development of the Indonesian language as a powerful national language. Advanced research on this topic will

provide a deeper insight into language trends in the public media as well as how we can maintain the quality of Indonesian language in this digital age.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

The influence of social media on the use of the Indonesian language also covers the aspects of globalization. Social media facilitates connections with individuals from different countries and cultures, which also influences the way that Indonesia is spoken. There are many terms and phrases in English that have been translated or adopted into Indonesian language through social media. It describes how today's global culture influences the development of contemporary Indonesia. However, not only are positive changes in the use of the Indonesian language on social media, there are also potential negative impacts. For example, the use of rude language, insult, and inappropriate content is often found on social media. This could jeopardize the authenticity and quality of the Indonesian language as the official language of the country. In addition, problems related to proper understanding of the Indonesian language also arise, where social media users may misunderstand or ignore correct grammar norms.

METHODOLOGY

This research is a qualitative study that uses the method of narrative analysis with a library research approach, using the purpose of describing the phenomena that exist, both in the present and in the past. The journal explores the evolution of communication styles in the public media, the impact of globalization on the use of the Indonesian language on the platform, as well as the ethics and quality of Indonesia's language in the context of social media.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Development of Communication Styles in Social Media

Based on the results of research on the evolution of communication styles in social media, a number of findings are known that provide a deeper understanding of the change of contemporary Indonesian language in the context of social media platforms, as follows:

1. The use of Emoji and Symbols: Research results show that emoji and symbols are very commonly used in the social media to express emotions and sentiments. Emoji is widely used to enrich visual communication, which creates an additional dimension in expression. It suggests that the emoji has become an integral part of the language of Indonesia on social media.
2. Use of abbreviations and acronyms: Abbreviation and acronyms such as "LOL," "BRB," and "OMG" are a significant part of the Indonesian language on social media. They are used to save character and facilitate quick communication, especially in informal conversations.
3. Slang and Style Language: Research found that slang and style language also flourished in social media. Users often create new words or phrases

- that are only understood by a particular group. It reflects the creativity and social identity of the Indonesian language on social media platforms.
4. **Adaptation of Foreign Words:** There is a tendency in the use of foreign words or phrases in Indonesia in social media. It is often associated with global trends and worldwide pop culture, and the usage of these foreign words reflects how the Indonesian language adapts to external influences.
 5. **Creativity and Innovation:** Research highlights the high level of creativity and innovation in the use of language in social media. Users often create meme, word games, and joke languages that become viral. It reflects the way social media facilitates creative and dynamic social interactions.
 6. **Language diversity:** Research confirms cultural and linguistic diversity in social media. Users from different cultural backgrounds can communicate in Indonesian on social media platforms. It creates a language that reflects cultural diversity and intercultural interaction.
 7. **Differences with formal languages:** Although informal languages on social media are growing rapidly, research also confirms differences with official languages. Formal language is still needed in contexts like work, academics, and government, and these differences are important to understand.

The findings from this study provide a deeper understanding of the evolution of communication styles in the public media and how public media has become a platform that has influenced changes in the use of the Indonesian language. It also reflects how social media platforms have become places where languages have become more expressive, relaxed, and creative. With a more profound understanding of this change, we can identify its positive and negative implications as well as consider how to involve social media users to nurture and develop the Indonesia language in this digital age.

The Influence of Globalization on Indonesian Language in Social Media

Based on the research, there are several influences of globalization on the Indonesian language in social media, namely:

1. The increasingly strong global influence has brought a new culture to Indonesia. Advances in social media technology allow individuals to connect more easily, even if they are remote. Language, as one of the cultural elements, contributes to the life of Indonesian people. This causes foreign languages to become increasingly dominant, threatening the Indonesian language in the country.
2. Globalization threatens the existence of the Indonesian language because there are no longer cross-cultural boundaries. In addition, the exclusiveness in the use of foreign languages has resulted in the younger generation tending to use a language mix when interacting on social media.
3. The use of the Indonesian language in social media by the generation of millennials and zilenials has declined in the era of globalization 4.0.

4. Too many users of Gaul language in the age of globalisation can make the position of the language of Indonesia as a national identity increasingly losing its identity.

Research results show that globalization affects the use of the Indonesian language on social media. The growth of foreign languages threatens the presence of the Indonesian language on social media. Moreover, millennials and Zelenia generations have experienced a decline in the use of the language in the era of globalization 4.0. Therefore, efforts are needed to strengthen the presence of the Indonesian language on social media so as not to be overwhelmed by the influence of globalization. One way to do that is to use social media to encourage people to learn Indonesian.

Ethics and Quality of Indonesian Language in Social Media

The ethics and quality of the Indonesian language in social media is an aspect that needs attention. The following are some findings related to the ethics and quality of Indonesian language on the platform:

1. Good communication ethics in social media involves a ban on the use of rude, provocative, pornographic content, or smelling SARA, as well as not sharing false information or infringing copyright, and giving relevant comments.
2. Language ethics on social media can be described as a pattern of behaviour in interacting, expressing opinions, or commenting on social networks.
3. Using informal and non-provoking language in communication on the social media may underestimate existing ethical principles.

The results suggest that the importance of ethics and quality of Indonesian language on social media platforms. Positive communication ethics there involves using words that are polite, not rude, not provocative, not vulgar, and not discriminatory. Moreover, language ethics in social media also includes the use of language in accordance with Indonesian language rules. A misunderstanding of language ethics in social media can lead to an inappropriate change of meaning and violate Indonesian language norms. Therefore, efforts are needed to raise awareness about Indonesian ethics and standards in social media, including the teaching and enforcement of strong sanctions by the authorities against users of social media who violate these standards.

From the results of several previous studies, it can be concluded that social media has an important influence on the use of contemporary Indonesian language. The following are some of the effects of social media on the use of Indonesian language today:

1. The emergence of informal language use in social media posts creates a more dynamic, short, and creative impression of language, with a tendency to shorten or replace long words.
2. Social media is often a place where non-formal language usage becomes commonplace.

3. Using informal languages can interfere with the comprehensive understanding of language.
4. Changes in the language of Indonesia people bring the influence of foreign identity into everyday life, with the good and correct use of language beginning to fade away due to the presence of westernization, resulting in a change in the way of speaking on social media.
5. The use of informal languages that violates the norms of the Indonesians language can threaten the position of Indonesia language as a distinctive national identity.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The use of Gaul or informal language in social media posts and the use of less formal language is the negative impact of social media on the current use of the Indonesian language. Consequently, efforts need to be made to raise ethical awareness and quality of the Indonesia language on such platforms. One of the steps that can be taken is to provide education on the ethics and quality of using the Indonesian language on social media. In addition, there is a need for strong sanctions from the law enforcement agencies on the users of social media who violate the ethical quality and language of Indonesia.

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